

Solid Liquid Separation of Manure and Climate Outcomes: Literature Review

Technical Advisory Network for Climate Smart
Agricultural Practices

June 30, 2025

ABOUT THE TECHNICAL ADVISORY NETWORK FOR CLIMATE SMART AGRICULTURAL PRACTICES

The Network emerged from a project of the [Meridian Institute](#) to better align Natural Resource Conservation Service (NRCS) Conservation Practice Standards with the best available science on GHG mitigation. In May 2024, Meridian Institute assembled six technical work groups (TWGs) to provide up-to-date scientific analysis of the impact of conservation practice adoption on GHG emissions and make technical recommendations regarding how best to achieve climate mitigation through those practices. The TWGs were comprised of academic scientists who are well regarded in their chosen field as well as scientists working within nongovernmental organizations focused on one or more of the chosen categories of interest: nutrient management, manure management, enteric methane, soil carbon, agroforestry, and grazing lands.

The technical work groups first identified agricultural practices in the six areas of interest for which evidence indicates considerable potential to reduce GHG emissions based on raw mitigation potential and adoption considerations. In August 2024 Meridian entered into a Contribution Agreement with NRCS to conduct literature reviews of the GHG emissions impacts of 39 practices, individually and in commonly practiced combinations. Meridian staff and TWG chairs and members worked with the NRCS National Discipline Leads to scope the reports and refine technical guidance regarding how best to implement practices to achieve GHG mitigation. The TWGs then conducted literature reviews, first and second-order meta-analyses, and modeling scenarios to identify the circumstances in which there is strong scientific evidence that the agricultural practices identified are likely to have net GHG benefits as well as implementation guidance for maximizing those benefits. The TWGs generated more than a dozen reports, which were delivered to NRCS in June 2025.

With the closing of Meridian Institute in mid-2025, the six technical working groups assembled by Meridian decided to establish the Network to provide a platform for sharing the work undertaken with a diversity of interested stakeholders and to support future collaboration within and/or across technical working groups. Slightly modified versions of the reports delivered to NRCS, such as this report, have been issued publicly by the Network and findings from several groups will be published in academic journals. The Network may also create briefs to summarize findings and technical recommendations for field conservationists and other interested stakeholders.

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Introduction

The environmental impacts of agricultural systems, including livestock production, are an increasing concern for policymakers, particularly in developed nations (Vieux et al., 2012). In particular, greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions are of concern because livestock production is estimated to produce 7.1 gigatons (14.5%) of carbon dioxide equivalents (CO₂-eq) per year of all global GHG emissions (Gerber et al., 2013) primarily in the form of carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), and nitrous oxide (N₂O). After GHG emissions from enteric fermentation (46%) and animal feed (23%), manure management accounts for approximately 13% of global GHG emissions from livestock production (Yan et al., 2024). Moreover, livestock manure management contributes 12-41% of CH₄ and 30-50% of N₂O of the total global agricultural emissions (Chadwick et al., 2011; Owen and Silver, 2015; Yusuf et al., 2012). In the United States, manure management accounts for approximately 14% of the total GHG from the agriculture sector (EPA, 2025). GHG emissions occur at all stages of manure management including animal housing (upstream), storage, treatment, and land application (downstream) (Chadwick et al., 2011; Hou et al., 2015). Livestock manure is rich in nutrients and organic matter, making it a valuable soil amendment that can replace significant amounts of mineral fertilizers. However, consolidation and spatial concentration of animal production and manure generation have created hotspots of nutrient accumulation, increasing environmental impacts including GHG emissions. In addition, there is often a need to transport manure slurry to distant crop fields, creating a disconnect between its generation and end-use.

Cattle, including dairy and non-dairy, and swine are the largest producers of manure slurries globally (Gerber et al., 2013) and in the United States (USDA, n.d.). Slurries, a mixture of feces, urine, bedding material, and water, are generally liquid containing 4 – 15 % solids, or dry matter (Dalby et al., 2021; Pain and Menzi, 2011). Slurry is often stored within slurry pits, outdoor storage tanks and lagoons for up to 1 year (with six months being common practice) before processing for land application (Ambrose et al., 2023; Owen and Silver, 2015). During this storage time, the facilities are usually in an anaerobic (Aguirre-Villegas et al., 2019) state resulting in emissions of CH₄, NH₃, and N₂O (Baral et al., 2018).

Solid-liquid separation (SLS) is an on-site manure processing technology that separates manure slurry into a liquid fraction with reduced total solids (TS) and a solid fraction rich in organic matter, TS, and phosphorous through physical and chemical methods. Separation processes can aid in manure recycling as the solid fraction, consisting of mainly undigested fibers, can be stacked, composted, dried, and recycled as a bedding material, subsequently reducing liquid manure storage requirements (Husfeldt et al., 2012). The liquid fraction, rich in soluble N, can be directly field applied as a fertilizer (Aguirre-Villegas et al., 2019; Guilayn et al., 2019), and overall, SLS systems can also result in lower costs to transport manure nutrients greater distances (Feng et al., 2023).

Solid liquid separation also has the potential to reduce anaerobic degradation, and thus, the GHG emissions from organic matter in stored slurries by reducing the volatile solids (VS) content (VanderZaag et al., 2018). Solid-liquid separation is part of a multi-step manure management process which includes upstream (indirect); during separation (indirect and direct); and downstream (direct) factors. Upstream factors can include animal type (most commonly cattle and pig), animal diet, manure collection methods (e.g., scraping, washing, inclusion of bedding in waste stream), and climatic conditions. Factors during separation can include SLS method, efficiency, and operation and maintenance. Downstream factors can include solid and liquid storage, climate (e.g., precipitation, temperature), and solid and liquid fate (e.g.,

composting of solid fraction, land application). These factors are rarely standardized between producers, complicating efforts to broadly quantify the overall efficiency of SLS and to study the effects of SLS technologies as a source or sink of GHG emissions.

This study reviews current literature focused on GHG emissions during the storage of solid and liquid manure slurry separates and summarizes separation efficiencies, and changes in N₂O, CH₄, and NH₃ emissions in solid and liquid fractions after SLS and SLS combined with other manure management practices.

Literature review search methods

DATA SOURCES AND SELECTION CRITERIA

The literature review used Web of Science (WOS) and Agricola to search for studies focused on the effects of solid-liquid manure separation (SLS) technologies on GHG emissions. Search key-word terms included “solid-liquid separation” and “greenhouse gas emissions”. A total of 137 and 69 articles were returned from the Web of Science and Agricola searches, respectively (Table S1). The Agricola search revealed 10 articles that had not been returned by the Web of Science search. Additionally, the Dairy Conservation Navigator (<https://www.dairyconservation.org/practices-and-technology>) was explored to identify citations relevant to SLS practices and technologies. All articles were entered into a literature review template and were reviewed for relevant criteria (Table 1).

Seven studies classified as review or meta-analyses were returned in the WOS and Agricola searches. Review and meta-analysis articles were further reviewed to identify any cited articles that were not returned in our original searches. These studies were added to our database and reviewed for the criteria in Table 1.

In the first screening, 77 articles were retained based on the main criteria requirement that the studies report measured or modeled GHG emissions. Six studies not reporting GHG emissions were included in the first screening as they reported separation efficiencies that were valuable to the analysis. The second screening followed the methods outlined in a recent meta-analysis (Zhang et.al., 2022) which included the following criteria:

1. A control group (no SLS) and a treatment group (with SLS) were used in the study.
2. Separation efficiency was calculated for at least one of the following slurry components in the control and treatment groups: dry matter (DM), volatile solids (VS), total nitrogen (TN), total ammonia nitrogen (TAN).
3. Measurements were made of at least one of the following gases: NH₃, N₂O, and CH₄.

Our original search results for GHG emissions included all the studies reported in the Zhang et.al., 2022 meta-analysis that reported GHG emissions and three studies that did not appear in the meta-analysis. These studies were also reviewed to note if volatile solids and partitioning of organic matter into degradable and non-degradable forms were reported.

Database characterization

Among the 71 records retained in the literature review, 29 SLS treatment combinations were represented for both animal types (Table 2). Of these, twenty SLS combinations were used in cattle production and sixteen combinations were used in swine production. Eight SLS combinations were used to process combined feedstocks which included mixtures of cattle and swine slurry, cattle or swine slurries combined with animal production by products e.g., bedding, animal and human food waste, and urban organic wastes. Screw press was the most common SLS technology used in both cattle (10 studies) and swine production (7 studies) followed by anaerobic digestion combined with screw press for cattle and centrifuge for swine slurry processing with 5 and 4 studies, respectively (Table 2).

The largest number of retained studies were performed at the farm or field scale (37%), followed by lab scale studies (25%), pilot scale (20%), and modeling studies (18%) (Table 3). Cattle and dairy systems made up approximately half of the studies followed by swine (31%), and mixed animal slurries/other feedstocks (19%). Studies conducted in European countries made up 63% of the total followed by the United States and Canada (28%), with China, Japan, and Brazil making up the balance (Table 3).

Separation efficiencies

The 71 retained studies were further limited using the criteria outlined in the meta-analysis by (Zhang et al., 2022) and separation efficiencies for SLS and SLS and other manure management combinations were summarized from data presented in Supplemental Table 1.

Separation efficiency can vary with slurry type and the operational parameters of the methods e.g., sieve size, g-force of centrifuge and screw press separation may be more suitable for slurries with high fiber content than centrifuge separation which may clog. The separation of total ammonia nitrogen (TAN) into solid and liquid fractions can have implications for NH₃ and N₂O emissions whereas the separation of volatile solids (VS) and dry matter (DM) out of liquid fractions may limit substrates for anaerobic biodegradability limiting methanogenesis and subsequent CH₄ emissions.

SEPARATION EFFICIENCY CALCULATED BY MASS BALANCE

The solid and liquid separation efficiencies are most accurately measured using a mass balance approach using the following equation when masses of raw slurry (RS), liquid fraction (LF), and solid fraction (SF) are collected:

$$SE_{SF} = SF_{\text{mass}}/RS_{\text{mass}}$$

$$SE_{LF} = LF_{\text{mass}}/RS_{\text{mass}}$$

Where SF_{mass} and LF_{mass} represent the mass of the solid fraction and liquid fraction after separation, and RS_{mass} represents the mass of the input unseparated RS.

However, the mass balance approach is difficult to perform under farm production scenarios due to the design and on-farm operations of SLS systems. For example, the mass balance approach was only used in 14% of retained studies.

SEPARATION EFFICIENCY CALCULATED USING CONCENTRATIONS

Where masses of raw slurry and separated solid and liquid fractions are not directly measured, separation efficiencies can be calculated using the concentrations of slurry components using the following equations (Svarovsky, 2001):

$$SE_{LF} = (X_{RS} - X_{SF}) / (X_{LF} - X_{SF})$$

$$SE_{SF} = (X_{RS} - X_{LF}) / (X_{SF} - X_{LF})$$

Zhang et. al., 2022 calculated separation efficiencies from 45 peer-reviewed studies for a total of 26 solid-liquid separation processes including mechanical separation and combination technologies.

SEPARATION EFFICIENCIES FOR CATTLE SYSTEMS (% RETAINED IN SOLID FRACTION)

At the farm scale, untreated slurry separated by screw press and centrifuge had the highest separation efficiencies for DM and total nitrogen (TN) with screw press separation slightly outperforming centrifuge separation (Table 4). Separation efficiencies for TS and VS were highest when a combination of anaerobic digestion and centrifuge separation was used. Overall, separation efficiencies for DM, TS, VS, and TAN were the highest when separation was performed in the laboratory by centrifuge (for DM and TAN) and by mechanical sieving (for TS, VS, and TN). At pilot scales, separation efficiencies were generally lower than for farm and laboratory scales, with centrifuge and screw press resulting in the highest efficiencies for DM and TN, respectively.

SEPARATION EFFICIENCIES FOR SWINE SYSTEMS (% RETAINED IN SOLID FRACTION)

There were 18 and 15 pre-treatment and SLS combinations reported for swine studies at the farm and lab scale, respectively. Separation efficiencies were overall higher in laboratory studies than farm scale studies for DM, TN, and TAN in swine studies (Table 5). In farm scale studies, there was not a discernable difference between SLS and SLS combinations for any components in untreated slurry. Acidification and anaerobic digestion pre-treatments did not substantially affect separation efficiencies at the farm scale except the combination of acidification, filter band, and flocculation resulted in the highest separation efficiencies for DM, TN, and TAN. Anaerobic digestion followed by rotary screen separation had the lowest separation efficiencies for all components at the farm scale.

Most treatments outperformed screw press separation for untreated swine slurry in laboratory studies for DM, TN, and TAN. (Table 5). Sediment settling and sediment settling combined with polyacrylamide resulted in the highest separation efficiencies for TN and TAN, and flocculation resulted in the highest efficiency for DM. Acidification, acidification plus anaerobic digestion, and anaerobic digestion pre-treatments appeared to lower separation efficiencies as compared to untreated slurry.

Greenhouse gas emissions

The effects of SLS on GHG emissions have been examined and summarized in recent review articles (Ambrose et al., 2023; Kupper et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2022). In each of these studies, efforts were made to report GHG emissions as percent reductions either from solid and liquid separates or the combination of both as compared to emissions from stored raw manure. (Kupper et al., 2020) found in their review overall 36, 22, and 31, different ways for reporting emissions were found for NH₃, N₂O, and CH₄, respectively, highlighting the variability and therefore difficulty in comparing studies. These authors apply and suggest that future studies apply unit standardization (e.g., g m⁻²h⁻¹ or d⁻¹) for reporting GHG emissions.

AMMONIA EMISSIONS

Kupper et al., 2020 report an increase in NH₃ emissions from the liquid fraction after SLS and SLS after anaerobic digestion of cattle slurry, the former being statistically significant (Table 6). These results were from treatments within 7 laboratory experiments. The increased NH₃ emissions were attributed to the diminished solids content of the liquid fraction reducing the formation of a natural crust which can provide an effective barrier leading to reductions in NH₃ (Aguerre et al., 2012; Wood et al., 2012). SLS and acidification in combination with SLS of swine slurry resulted in close to zero and substantial reductions in average emissions of NH₃, respectively (Table 6). The minimal effect of SLS alone on NH₃ emissions as compared to untreated slurry could be because swine exhibits a lower ability to form a natural crust. However, in one study that combined acidification with SLS, substantial reductions in NH₃ emissions were reported.

Zhang et al, 2022 reported that SLS technologies tended to increase NH₃ emissions when solid and liquid fractions from cattle and swine production were considered together with no pretreatment, anaerobic digestion, or the whole dataset and that losses were mainly from the liquid fraction. Average NH₃ percent losses from the separated solid fraction are consistently lower than from raw slurry when animal type and pre-treatment are considered separately (Table 7). However, for cattle, NH₃ emissions increased in the liquid fraction after SLS of untreated slurry, and for swine, NH₃ emissions increased in the liquid fraction after acidification and anaerobic digestion pretreatments (Table 7).

NITROUS OXIDE EMISSIONS

For cattle, lower average percent N₂O emissions as compared to raw slurry were reported from the separated liquid fraction from both untreated and anaerobic digestion pretreatment (Table 6). However, substantial N₂O emissions were reported for the liquid fraction of pig slurry with no pretreatment and with acidification. Similar reductions in percent N₂O emissions after separation were reported for liquid

fractions after no pretreatment and anaerobic digestion for cattle slurry and after anaerobic digestion and acidification plus digestion for swine slurry (Table 7). However, increased N₂O emissions compared to raw slurry were reported for the liquid fraction after SLS with no pretreatment and SLS after acidification for swine slurry. Nearly all pretreatment and SLS combinations resulted in increased N₂O emissions from the solid fraction for both cattle and swine slurries. Only screw press after anaerobic digestion (one study) for cattle and screw press after digestion and acidification plus digestion resulted in lower emissions from the solid fraction after separation (Table 7).

Overall, the application of SLS tends to increase N₂O emissions during storage and the increase is dominated by the solid fraction. Nitrous oxide is produced from the combined nitrification-denitrification process where nitrification occurs under aerobic conditions and converts NH₃ into nitrate. Denitrification occurs if conditions become anaerobic, such as hot spots in stored piles of compost (Amon et al., 2006), and can release N₂O through incomplete nitrate reduction (Kebreab et al., 2006) because there is less nitrate found in the liquid fraction denitrification and N₂O production is limited. Surface crusts are more likely to form on the solid fraction of separated cattle slurry providing the aerobic and anaerobic environments necessary for N₂O production (Chadwick et al., 2011; SOMMER et al., 2015).

METHANE EMISSIONS

Methane emissions were consistently reduced after SLS and pre-treatments + SLS as compared to raw slurry for both cattle and swine in the solid and liquid fractions (Table 6 and 7). SLS reduces volatile solids and dry matter content in liquid fraction reducing substrate for methanogenesis through anaerobic biodegradation (VanderZaag et al., 2018; Wood et al., 2012). Methane emissions from solids tend to be negligible due to mostly aerobic conditions during storage (Holly et al., 2017) and composting (Hou 2017).

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Tables and Supplemental Information

Table 1. Parameters extracted from initial literature search results of 136 returned articles from Web of Science and Agricola databases.

Parameter	Description
Animal type	Cattle or pig
Country	Location where the study was performed
Year	Study publication year
Authors	Study authors
Research scale	Laboratory, pilot, or farm scale. Studies modeling farm-scale processes were included as farm scale studies for this classification.
Separation efficiency	Separation efficiency measured or modeled.
Separation efficiency components	Separation efficiency measured for which components.
GHG emissions measurement	GHG emissions directly measured or estimated using modeling
Feedstock (SLS inputs)	Untreated manure; combined with food waste, silage, bedding;
Slurry treatment	Untreated; other manure processing treatments applied pre- or post-SLS. Anaerobic digestion, chemical flocculation, other SLS methods
Manure characterization	Component composition of raw manure and solid and liquid separates
Raw manure TS range	TS reported for raw manure and solid and liquid separates
Fate of solid & liquid fraction	Composting, anaerobic digestion, land application
Particle size	Particle size measured and reported
Composite samples	Were samples composited prior to component analysis or separation
Seasonal measurements	Season in which measurements were collected
Organic matter partitioning	Organic matter partitioned into degradable or non-degradable fractions

Type of study: As defined by (Kupper et al., 2020). Farm-scale: measurements carried out at real-world storage facilities at a farm site. Pilot-scale and laboratory-scale: measurements conducted under controlled conditions in experimental vessels. Due to a lack of definition for these study types, a discrimination according to the following characteristics was employed: Pilot-scale: volume of slurry investigated: ≥ 500 L with experimental vessels situated outdoors, with or without a shelter and submitted to ambient meteorological conditions. Laboratory-scale: volume of slurry investigated: < 500 L. Most of the studies defined as laboratory-scale studies were conducted indoors in a temperature-controlled room.

Table 2. Representation of solid-liquid separation technologies and combinations of solid-liquid separation and other manure management processes for cattle, swine, and combined feedstocks in retained studies. Combined feedstocks may include mixtures of cattle and swine slurries; slurries mixed with food waste, bedding, municipal organic wastes. PAM – Polyacrylamide.

Treatment	Cattle	Swine	Combined feedstock
Screw press alone	10	7	3
Centrifuge	2	4	3
Screen	-	1	-
Anaerobic digestion + Screw press	5	1	1
Anaerobic digestion +rotary sieve	1	-	-
Screw press + PAM	2	-	-
Screw press + centrifuge	1	-	1
Screw press + coagulation	-	1	-
Screw press + acidification	1	1	-
Anaerobic digestion + centrifuge	2	-	1
Anaerobic digestion + screen	2	-	-
Anaerobic digestion + SLS	1	-	-
Acidification + centrifuge	1	1	-
Rotating sieve	-	-	-
Lab-mechanical separation	2	1	1
Lab-centrifuge + acidification	1	-	1
Lab - sieve	1	1	-
Sloped screen+ Horiz. scraped	1	-	-
Chemical flocculation	1	-	-
Aerobic treatment	-	2	-
Cationic polymer+ Filter press	-	1	-
Settling tank + chemical flocculation	-	2	-
Weeping wall	1	-	-
unspecified	5	2	1
Roller press	1	-	-
Filter band + screw press	-	1	-
PAM + screen	-	2	-
PAM + belt	-	2	-
Anaerobic Digestion + Screen	1	-	-

Table 3. Number of studies classified by research scale from 71 retained studies.

Parameter	From retained studies
Research scale	
Farm	26
Pilot	14
Lab	18
Modeling	13
Animal type	
Cattle	35
Swine	22
Mixed animal + other	14
Study location	
North America	20
Europe	45
China	4
Japan	1
Brazil	1

Table 4. Separation efficiencies reported as percent change after treatment as compared to raw slurry storage for studies in cattle systems at the farm, pilot, and laboratory scales.

	Pre-treatment	SLS technology	Constituent separation efficiency (%)									
			DM	n	TS	n	VS	n	TN	n	TAN	n
Farm Scale												
	Untreated	Screw press	69.4	2	43.4	6	47.1	3	39.0	8	7.6	8
		Centrifuge	62.7	1	na	-	na	-	28.7	1	16.1	1
	Anaerobic digestion	Screw press	32.4	13	42.8	6	48.8	5	13.0	19	6.8	19
		Centrifuge	na	-	49.9	1	56.4	1	14.3	1	0.8	1
		Roller press	na	-	27.9	4	32.7	4	11.8	4	4.9	4
		Screw extractor+rotary screen	61.8	1	na	-	58	1	31.5	1	na	-
Pilot Scale												
	Untreated	Screw press	40.9	3	na	-	na	-	18.3	3	9.7	3
		Centrifuge	42.5	2	na	-	na	-	15.8	2	7.1	2
		Roller press	11.9	2	na	-	na	-	3.6	2	3.0	2
Lab Scale												
	Untreated	Screw press	na	-	53.3	5	58.6	5	19.2	3	14.3	2
		Centrifuge	67.4	2	na	-	na	-	51.3	2	55.3	1
		Belt press	41.3	1	46.8	1	na	-	19.3	1	7.0	1
		Drainage + flocculation	46.6	2	na	-	na	-	34.7	2	na	-
		Sieving	na	-	79.1	1	79.9	1	59.4	1	na	-

Adapted from Supplemental Table 1 (Zhang et. al., 2022)

Table 5. Separation efficiencies reported as percent change after treatment as compared to raw slurry storage for studies in swine systems at the farm and laboratory scales.

Pre-treatment	SLS technology	Constituent separation efficiency (%)										
		DM	n	TS	n	VS	n	TN	n	TAN	n	
Farm Scale												
Untreated	Screw press	56.1	2	35.3	3	62.5	3	24.6	3	20.8	3	
	Centrifuge	59.2	4	48.3	1	81.5	1	19.8	5	14.6	4	
	Screw press+centrifuge	na	-	55.6	1	na	-	18.4	1	9.5	1	
	Filter band+screw press	na	-	38.0	1	63.9	1	28.0	1	na	-	
	Filter band+screw press+rotary sieve	na	-	61.0	1	100.3	1	33.0	1	na	-	
	Centrifuge + flocculation	na	-	74.4	1	na	-	41.9	1	na	-	
	Rotary press + flocculation	na	-	73.4	1	na	-	38.1	1	na	-	
	Belt filtration + flocculation	na	-	na	-	62.7	1	17.4	1	15.0	1	
	PAM+rotating screen+filter press+air flotation	na	-	68.4	2	na	-	38.0	2	16.4	2	
Acidification	Screw press	51.5	2	na	-	78.5	2	30.8	2	24.2	2	
	Centrifuge	48.4	1	na	-	57.6	1	15.3	1	9.9	1	
	Belt filtration + flocculation	26.0	1	na	-	31.7	1	8.9	1	7.7	1	
	Filter band + flocculation	91.5	1	na	-	na	-	71.2	1	53.8	1	
Anaerobic Digestion	Screw press	31.6	5	na	-	na	-	9.3	5	6.0	5	
	Centrifuge	47.5	1	na	-	na	-	13.4	1	6	1	
	Rotary screen	6.5	1	na	-	7.8	1	2.0	1	0.4	1	
Lab Scale												
Untreated	Screw press	37.5	2	na	-	na	-	13.6	1	7.8	1	
	Centrifuge	72.6	6	na	-	na	-	39.4	5	23.1	4	
	Sediment settling	89.0	1	na	-	na	-	90.1	1	88	1	
	Sediment settling +PAM	89.2	1	na	-	na	-	111.7	1	84.9	1	
	Sieving	87.3	1	na	-	na	-	64.3	1	48.5	1	
	Sieving + PAM	90.8	1	na	-	na	-	93.1	1	85	1	
	Press filtration	51.0	1	na	-	na	-	4.4	1	na	-	
	Drainage + flocculation	63.8	2	na	-	na	-	13.6	2	na	-	
	flocculation	98.5	1	na	-	na	-	65.0	1	44.4	1	
	Centrifuge+flocculation	90.3	1	na	-	na	-	63.6	1	35.1	1	
acidification	Screw press	102.4	1	32.7	3	39.5	3	13.7	3	8.5	3	
	Drum screen	na	-	33.5	1	42.7	1	11.2	1	10.9	1	
	centrifuge	61.0	3	na	-	na	-	31.3	3	15.7	3	

Acidification +digestion	Screw press	na	-	29.8	3	36.5	3	24.9	3	15.0	3
digestion	Screw press	na	-	30.6	1	38.3	1	13.0	1	8.7	1

Adapted from Supplemental Table 1 (Zhang et. al., 2022)

Table 6. Greenhouse gas emissions change during storage of separated liquid fraction (% change of emissions on an area or volume basis) during storage of treated slurry relative to untreated slurry. Negative numbers indicate a reduction in emissions. Positive numbers indicate an increase in emissions.

	Treatment	n	NH ₃	std	n	N ₂ O	std	n	CH ₄	std
Cattle										
	SLS	12	22.5*	21	6	-42.7*	36	10	-32.2*	27
	AD+SLS	1	37.0	--	1	-27.3	--	1	-69.4	--
Swine										
	SLS	7	0.7	18	1	257.5	--	7	-39.5*	39
	Acidification+SLS	1	-75.4	--	1	143.5	--	1	-95.2	--

Adapted from Kupper et al., 2020 supplemental Table 6

Table 7. Percent change in NH₃, N₂O, and CH₄ emissions from separated solid and liquid component compared with raw slurry.

			NH ₃		N ₂ O		CH ₄	
			Solid	Liquid	Solid	Liquid	Solid	Liquid
Cattle								
Digestion	Roller Press (n=5)							
	Screw press (n=1)			-30.07				
Untreated	Screw press (n=6)							
	Screw press + PAM (n=1)		-97.2	58.6	740.6	-64.4	-79.3	-84.0
Swine								
Untreated	Screw press (n=3)							
	PAM+rotating screen+filter press+air floatation (n= 2)		-13.96	-12.08	na	na	na	na
Acidification	Screw press (n=1)		-74.5	235.1	1139.5	37.5	-15.7	-41.9
Digestion	Screw press (n=1)		-27.0	824.5	-48.0	-97.3	-96.9	37.5
Acidification+digestion	Screw press (n=1)		-93.9	-49.7	-66.8	-64.1	-58.3	-6.2

Adapted from Supplemental Table 1 (Zhang et. al., 2022)